

SQANTI3 report

Unique Genes: 11827

Unique Isoforms: 48245

Gene Classification

Category	Genes, count
Annotated Genes	11822
Novel Genes	5

Transcript Classification

Category	Isoforms, count
FSM	18504
ISM	1631
NIC	27293
NNC	18
Genic Genomic	1
Antisense	6
Fusion	792
Intergenic	0
Genic Intron	0

Splice Junction Classification

Category	SJs, count	Percent
Known canonical	129549	93.27
Known Non-canonical	101	0.07
Novel canonical	9193	6.62
Novel Non-canonical	55	0.04

Gene Characterization

Number of Isoforms per Gene

Number of Isoforms per Gene

Known vs Novel Genes

Distribution of Mono- vs Multi-Exon Transcripts

Structural Categories by Transcript Length

All Transcript Lengths Distribution

Transcript Lengths Distribution by Structural Category

Mono- vs Multi- Exon Transcript Lengths Distribution

Structural Isoform Characterization

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across FSM

Isoform Distribution Across ISM

Isoform Distribution Across NNC

Isoform Distribution Across NIC

Isoform Distribution Across Fusion

Transcript Lengths by Structural Classification

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Structural Classification

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Subcategories

Length Distribution of Matched Reference Transcripts

Applicable Only to FSM and ISM Categories

Exon Count Distribution of Matched Reference Transcripts

Applicable Only to FSM and ISM Categories

Splice Junction Characterization

Distribution of Splice Junctions by Structural Classification

Distribution of Transcripts by Splice Junctions

RT-Switching All Junctions

Unique Junctions RT-switching

Comparison With Annotated TSS and TTS

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for FSM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for FSM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS)

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS)

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for ISM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for ISM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

*Comparison With Annotated TSS and TTS
by Subcategories*

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 3'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 3'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 3'5'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 3'5'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 5'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 5'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Reference Match

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Reference Match

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM 3' Fragment

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM 3' Fragment

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM Internal Fragment

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM Internal Fragment

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM A5' Fragment

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM A5' Fragment

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM Intron Retention

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM Intron Retention

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

PolyA Distance Analysis

Distance of Detected PolyA Motif From 3' end

Frequency of PolyA Motifs

Number of polyA Motifs Detected

Category	Count	polyA Detected	%
FSM	18504	15354	83
ISM	1631	1163	71
NIC	27293	22558	83
NNC	18	18	100
Genic Genomic	1	0	0
Antisense	6	1	17
Fusion	792	593	75

Motif	Count	%
AATAAA	27324	68.8
ATTAAA	6275	15.8
AGTAAA	1219	3.1
TATAAA	866	2.2
CATAAA	594	1.5
AATATA	501	1.3
TTTAAA	465	1.2
AATACA	443	1.1
GATAAA	386	1.0
AAGAAA	327	0.8
AAAAAG	321	0.8
ACTAAA	265	0.7
AATAGA	244	0.6
AATGAA	236	0.6
AAAACA	178	0.4
GGGGCT	43	0.1

Distance of Detected PolyA Motif From 3' End by Non-FSM/ISM Subcategories

Number of polyA Motifs Detected

Subcategory	Count	polyA Detected	%
Alternative 3'end	6441	5100	79
Alternative 3'5'end	1896	1515	80
Alternative 5'end	2098	1785	85
Reference match	7772	6742	87
3' fragment	696	541	78
Internal fragment	106	58	55
5' fragment	486	295	61
Comb. of annot. junctions	7701	6251	81
Comb. of annot. splice sites	7835	6538	83
Intron retention	12365	10237	83
Mono-exon by intron ret.	1	0	0
At least 1 annot. don./accept.	15	15	100
Mono-exon	307	213	69
Multi-exon	526	397	75

Frequency of PolyA Motifs

Motif	Count	%
AATAAA	27324	68.8
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AGTAAA	1219	3.1
TATAAA	866	2.2
CATAAA	594	1.5
AATATA	501	1.3
TTTAAA	465	1.2
AATACA	443	1.1
GATAAA	386	1.0
AAGAAA	327	0.8
AAAAAG	321	0.8
ACTAAA	265	0.7
AATAGA	244	0.6
AATGAA	236	0.6
AAAACA	178	0.4
GGGGCT	43	0.1

Redundancy Analysis

Reference Transcript Redundancy

Reference Transcript Redundancy

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Reference Transcript Redundancy

Only FSM with a polyA motif found

Reference Transcript Redundancy

Only ISM with a polyA motif found

Reference Transcript Redundancy

FSM+ISM with a polyA motif found

Intra-Priming Quality Check

Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Coding vs Non-Coding Possible Intra-Priming

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Features of Bad Quality

RT-switching

Non-Canonical Junctions

Nonsense-Mediated Decay by Structural Category

Quality Control Attributes Across Structural Categories

Features of Good Quality

Annotation Support

PolyA Support

All Canonical Junctions

Good Quality Control Attributes Across Structural Categories

